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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF DACLATASVIR AND SOFOSBUVIR IN DRUG PRODUCT BY RP-HPLC

M. Srinivasa Rao^{*}, Dr. K. Rambabu

Department of Chemistry, R V R & J C College of Engineering, Chowdavaram, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh – 522019.

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ABSTRACT

New Analytical method was developed for the estimation of Daclatasvir and Sofosbuvir in drug product by liquid chromatography. The chromatographic separation was achieved on C18 column (Phenyl XDB 250*4.6mm) at ambient temperature. The separation achieved employing a mobile phase consists of 0.1% v/v Trifluoro acetic acid in water : Acetonitrile(500:500). The flow rate was 1.0ml/ minute and ultra violet detector at 275nm. The average retention time for Daclatasvir and Sofosbuvir found to be 2.805 min and 3.743 min. the proposed method was validated for selectivity, precision, linearity and accuracy. All validation parameters were within the acceptable range. The assay methods were found to be linear from 12.0 – 36.0 µg/ml for Daclatasvir and 80.0 – 240.0 µg/ml of Sofosbuvir.

Corresponding author

M. Srinivasa Rao

Department of Chemistry,

R V R & J C College of Engineering,

Chowdavaram, Guntur,

Andhra Pradesh - 522019

kantipudirambabu@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

DACLATASVIR

Daclatasvir, sold under the trade name Daklinza, is a medication used in combination with other medications to treat hepatitis C (HCV). The other medications used in combination include sofosbuvir, ribavirin, and interferon, vary depending on the virus type and whether the person has cirrhosis. It is taken by mouth once a day.

Daclatasvir is chemically designated as Dimethyl N,N'-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4,4'-diylbis{1H-imidazole-5,2-diyl}[(2S)-pyrrolidine-2,1-diyl][(2S)-3-methyl-1-oxobutane-1,2-diyl])dicarbamate. Its molecular formula is C₄₀H₅₀N₈O₆, and its molecular weight is 738.89 g/mol

Structure of Daclatasvir.

SOFOSBUVIR

Sofosbuvir, sold under the brand name Sovaldi among others, is a medication used for the treatment of hepatitis C. It is only recommended with some combination of ribavirin, peginterferon-alfa, simeprevir, ledipasvir, daclatasvir, or velpatasvir. Cure rates are 30 to 97% depending on the type of hepatitis C virus involved. Safety during pregnancy is unclear; while, some of the medications used in combination may result in harm to the baby. It is taken by mouth.

Sofosbuvir is chemically designated as Isopropyl (2S)-2-[[[(2R,3R,4R,5R)-5-(2,4-dioxypyrimidin-1-yl)-4-fluoro-3-hydroxy-4-methyl-tetrahydrofuran-2-yl]methoxy-phenoxy-phosphoryl]amino]propanoate. Its molecular formula is C₂₂H₂₉FN₃O₉P, and its molecular weight is 529.453 g/mol.

Structure of Sofosbuvir.

EXPERIMENTAL:

Equipments:

The chromatographic technique performed on a waters 2695 with 2487 detector and Empower2 software, reversed phase C18 column (Phenyl XDB 250*4.6mm,5μ) as stationary phase, Ultrasonic cleaner, Scaletech analytical balance, Vacuum micro filtration unit with 0.45μ membrane filter was used in the study.

Materials:

Pharmaceutically pure sample of Daclatasvir/Sofosbuvir were obtained as gift samples from Fortune pharma training institute, Sri Sai Nagar colony, KPHB, Hyderabad, India.

HPLC-grade Methanol was from Qualigens reagents pvt ltd. Trifluoro acetic acid (AR grade) was from SD Fine Chem.

Chromatographic conditions

The sample separation was achieved on a (5 μ, 250 cm X 4.6 mm i.d.) Eclipse XDB-Phenyl C18 column, aided by mobile phase mixture of 0.1% v/v Trifluoro acetic acid in water: Acetonitrile (50:50). The flow rate was 1.0 ml/minute and ultra violet detector at 275nm that was filtered and degassed prior to use, Injection volume is 10 μl and ambient temperatures.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Buffer Preparation:

Taken accurately 1ml of Trifluoro acetic acid in 1000mL of water

Mobile phase:

Then added 50 volumes of buffer and 50 volumes of Acetonitrile mixed well and sonicated for 5 min.

Diluents:

Water: Acetonitrile 50:50 v\|v

Preparation of standard stock solution:

A 6 mg of pure Daclatasvir and 40 mg of Sofosbuvir were weighed and transferred to 50 ml of volumetric flask and dissolved in Diluent. The flask was shaken and volume was made up to mark with diluent to give a primary stock solution. From the above solution 2.0ml of solution is pipette out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to mark with water to give a solution containing 24.0µg/ml of Daclatasvir and 160 µg/ml Sofosbuvir.

Preparation of sample solution:

Accurately weighed twenty tablets were ground to obtain fine powder equivalent to 6mg of Daclatasvir and 40mg of Sofosbuvir sample were weighed and transferred to 50 ml of volumetric flask and dissolved in diluent. The flask was shaken and volume was made up to mark with diluent to give a primary stock solution. From the above solution 2.0 ml of solution is pipette out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to mark with diluents(Water) to give a solution containing 24.0 µg/ml of Daclatasvir and 160.0 µg/ml Sofosbuvir.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS**Determination Of Working Wavelength (λ max):**

10 mg of the Daclatasvir and Sofosbuvir standard drug is taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in Diluent and volume made up to the mark, from this solution 0.1ml is pipette into 10 ml volumetric flask and made upto the mark with the Water to give a concentration of 10 µg/ml. The above prepared solution is scanned in uv between 200-400 nm using Water as blank. The λ max was found to be 275nm

After several initial trails with mixtures of methanol, water, ACN and buffer in various combinations and proportions, a trail with a mobile phase mixture of 0.1%v/v Trifluoro acetic acid in water: Acetonitrile (50:50). The flow rate was 1.0 ml/ minute brought sharp peaks. The chromatogram was shown in Figure-1.

Figure: 1 Chromatogram of Daclatasvir and Sofosbuvir.

METHOD VALIDATION**Linearity:**

Linearity was studied by analyzing five standard solutions covering the range of 12.0 -36.0µg/ml for Daclatasvir and 80.0 – 240.0µg/ml Sofosbuvir. From the primary stock solution 1.0ml,1.5ml,2.0ml,2.5ml,3.0 ml of aliquots are pipette into 10 ml volumetric flasks and made up to the mark with the water to give a concentrations of 12.0 µg /mL , 18.0µg/mL ,24.0µg/mL ,30.0µg/mL and 36.0 µg/mL of Daclatasvir and 80.0µg/mL,120.0µg/mL ,160.0µg/mL ,200.0µg/mL and 240.0 µg/mL Sofosbuvir. Calibration curve with concentration verses peak areas was plotted by injecting the above prepared solutions and the obtained data were subjected to regression analysis using the least squares method.

Table No: 1: Linearity data of Daclatasvir.

Level	Concentration (mg/mL)	Peak area
50%	0.012	243484
75%	0.018	379620
100%	0.024	499346
125%	0.030	643330
150%	0.036	770596

FigureNo.2: Linearity (calibration) curve of Daclatasvir.

Table No: 2: Linearity data of Sofosbuvir.

Level	Concentration (mg/mL)	Peak area
50%	0.080	473932
75%	0.120	715863
100%	0.160	948361
125%	0.200	1190358
150%	0.240	1422045

FigureNo.3: Linearity (calibration) curve of Sofosbuvir.

RESULT

A linear relationship between peak areas versus concentrations was observed for Daclatasvir and Sofosbuvir in the range of 50% to 150% of nominal concentration. Correlation coefficient was 0.9997 and 1.0000 for both Daclatasvir and Sofosbuvir which prove that the method is linear in the range of 50% to 150%.

Limit of detection and limit of quantification:

The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were separately determined based on standard deviation of the y-intercept and the slope of the calibration curve by using the equations (1) and (2), respectively.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \sigma / S \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma / S \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where,

σ = the standard deviation of the response (STEYX)

S = the slope of the calibration curve

The slope S may be estimated from the calibration curve of the analyte.

Table no.3: LOD and LOQ values Calculated from calibration curve:

	Daclatasvir mg	Sofosbuvir mg
LOD	0.001	0.002
LOQ	0.003	0.005

Method precision (repeatability)

The precision of the method was checked by repeated preparation (n=6) of 24.0 μ g/ml of Daclatasvir and 160.0 μ g/ml Sofosbuvir without changing the parameter of the proposed chromatographic method. And measure the peak areas and retention times.

Table.4: Summary of peak areas for method precision of Daclatasvir.

Sample No	Retention time	Peak area	% Assay
1	2.808	506411	99.1
2	2.807	511193	98.9
3	2.805	505223	98.9
4	2.807	509294	99.5
5	2.805	505388	98.7
6	2.807	479589	98.9
Mean	2.807	502850	99.0
%RSD	0.04	2.31	0.28

Table.5: Summary of peak areas for method precision of Sofosbuvir.

Sample No	Retention time	Peak area	% Assay
1	3.735	955014	99.5
2	3.735	955683	99.8
3	3.733	956994	99.7
4	3.736	955986	99.9
5	3.733	950290	98.8
6	3.735	950886	99.1
Mean	3.735	954142	99.4
%RSD	0.03	0.30	0.44

RESULT

Results of variability were summarized in the above table. Percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) was found to be less than 2.0% which proves that method is precise.

Accuracy (recovery study):

The accuracy of the method was determined by calculating the recoveries of Daclatasvir and Sofosbuvir by analyzing solutions containing approximately 50%, 100% and 150% of the working strength of Daclatasvir and Sofosbuvir. The percentage recovery results obtained are listed in Table 6 & 7

Table No.6: Recovery data of Daclatasvir.

Level	S.NO	%Recovery of Daclatasvir	Average
50	1	100.2	99.7%
	2	99.9	
	3	99.0	
100	1	99.1	99.0%
	2	98.9	
	3	98.9	
150	1	99.4	99.6%
	2	99.8	
	3	99.6	

Table No.7: Recovery data of Sofosbuvir.

Level	S.NO	%Recovery of Sofosbuvir	Average
50	1	99.6	99.6%
	2	99.0	
	3	100.2	
100	1	99.5	99.6%
	2	99.8	
	3	99.7	
150	1	99.7	99.4%
	2	99.6	
	3	99.0	

RESULT

Results of accuracy study are presented in the above table. All the results indicate that the method is highly accurate.

Robustness:

Robustness is the measure of a method remain unaffected by small, deliberate changes in method parameters like flow rate and detection wavelength on assay of the analyte of interest. Here the detection wavelength varied ± 2 nm and flow rate was varied ± 0.2 ml/min. The results were shown in (Table no. 8&9)

Table No.8: Results of Daclatasvir.

Parameter	Rt of Daclatasvir	Theoretical plates	Asymmetry
Decreased flow rate (0.8ml/min)	3.484	9678	1.12
Increased flow rate (1.2ml/min)	2.349	7169	1.09
Wave Length 273nm	2.805	8379	1.12
277nm	2.811	8515	1.08

Table No.9: Results of Sofosbuvir.

Parameter	Rt of Sofosbuvir	Theoretical plates	Asymmetry
Decreased flow rate (0.8ml/min)	4.636	14868	1.11
Increased flow rate (1.2ml/min)	3.120	10723	1.08
Wave Length 273nm	3.732	12545	1.08
277nm	3.736	12584	1.09

RESULT

The results of Robustness of the present method had shown that changes are not significant we can say that the method is Robust.

Ruggedness:

The ruggedness of the method was studied by analyzing the sample and standard preparations by two analysts. The results were shown in Table no.10&11.

Table No.10: Results of Daclatasvir.

		%Assay	%RSD
Analyst-1	DACLATASVIR	99.1	0.14%
Analyst-2		98.9	

Table No.11: Results of Sofosbuvir.

		%Assay	%RSD
Analyst-1	SOFOSBUVIR	99.5	0.21%
Analyst-2		99.8	

RESULT

The % RSD assay values between two analysts was calculated, this indicates the method was rugged.

Table No.12: Summary of Daclatasvir.

S.NO	Parameter	Result	Acceptance criteria
1	System suitability		
	Theoretical plates	2.807	Not less than 2000
	Asymmetry	8438	Not more than 2.0
	Retention time	1.11	
	%RSD	0.38	Not more than 2.0
2	Specificity	Specific	Specific
3	Method precision(%RSD)	2.31	Not more than 2.0%
4	Linearity Range(mcg/ml)	12.0 -36.0	
	Correlation coefficient(r ²)	0.9997	Not less than 0.990
5	Accuracy (Mean % recovery)		97 - 103%
	50%	99.7	
	100%	99.0	
	150%	99.6	
6	Robustness	All the system suitability parameters are within the limits.	

*RSD = Relative standard deviation.

Table No.13: Summary of Sofosbuvir.

S.NO	Parameter	Result	Acceptance criteria
1	System suitability		
	Theoretical plates	3.734	Not less than 2000
	Asymmetry	12458	Not more than 2.0
	Retention time	1.08	
	%RSD	0.31	Not more than 2.0
2	Specificity	Specific	Specific
3	Method precision(%RSD)	0.30	Not more than 2.0%
4	Linearity Range(mcg/ml)	80.0 – 240.0	
	Correlation coefficient(r ²)	1.000	Not less than 0.990
5	Accuracy (Mean % recovery)		97 - 103%
	50%	99.6	
	100%	99.6	
	150%	99.4	
6	Robustness	All the system suitability parameters are within the limits.	

CONCLUSION

From the above experimental results it was concluded that, this newly developed method for the simultaneous estimation of DACLATASVIR and SOFOSBUVIR was found to be simple, precise, accurate and high resolution and shorter retention time makes this method more acceptable and cost effective and it can be effectively applied for routine analysis in research institutions, quality control department in meant in industries, approved testing laboratories.

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